

Search Mechanisms of Dimensions.ai

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Achieving success in the huge ocean of scientific research can be tricky. Researchers frequently spend endless hours searching through several articles, datasets, and other resources in pursuit of the information they require. Dimensions AI, a strong research tool developed to speed up the discovery process, comes in handy here.

Dimensions AI extends beyond conventional keyword searches. It has a unique search engine that combines extensive data coverage, interconnected information, and cutting-edge AI technology. This potent trio enables researchers to not only swiftly identify relevant information, but also obtain a better knowledge of the research landscape.

The details of Dimensions AI's search processes will be covered in the parts that follow, along with an examination of how these elements combine to provide an outstanding research experience. We'll look into the search engine's distinctive features and how Dimensions AI differs from other research tools.

What Dimensions is saying about themselves:

At the outset of the Dimensions project, we were certain that we wanted to do more than just build another A&I database. It was our intention to offer a new perspective on research data—a more transparent and all-inclusive data architecture that enabled users to investigate relationships among a variety of research data.

The project team also adopted that novel strategy. Digital Science, along with our portfolio firms ReadCube, Altmetric, Figshare, Symplectic, Digital Science Consultancy, and ÜberResearch, did not construct Dimensions by themselves. We collaborated closely with the scientific community throughout the project, and that relationship continues to drive new advances today.

Dimensions is unique and different from other scholarly databases in several key ways:

- **Comprehensive Database:** An extensive collection of research outputs, such as publications, grants, patents, clinical trials, databases, and policy papers, are captured by Dimensions. It had about 106 million publications as of December 2019, which is about 30% more than similar databases. Analysis choices are significantly increased by this inclusion.

- **Advanced Filtering Features:** Dimensions provides customers access to a large number of filtering features that enable accurate data selection. This guarantees that consumers will always be able to examine the data that best meets their requirements.
- **Holistic View of Impact:** By connecting publications with citations, grants, patents, clinical trials, datasets, and policy papers, Dimensions offers a more comprehensive picture than standard databases, which mostly concentrate on citations. A more thorough picture of the research landscape is provided by this interconnection.
- **Open Access to Citation Networks:** Dimensions makes over 106 million publications and 1.2 billion citations freely available, fostering serendipitous discoveries and helping the evaluation and extension of high-quality research.
- **Single Platform for Discovery and Analytics:** A&I databases and analytics tools are integrated into a single platform by Dimensions, which simplifies the user experience and boosts productivity. This is in contrast to other databases that keep their A&I databases and analytics tools apart.
- **Support for Research Community:** The scientometric research community can obtain Dimensions and the data it includes for free, which promotes the creation of the upcoming generation of indicators. Their dedication to bolstering the research ecosystem is consistent with their values and the DORA declaration for the appraisal of scientific research.

How do we search in Dimensions?

Dimensions is a comprehensive scholarly database designed to provide a rich context for research evaluation and discovery. It integrates various types of research outputs, including publications, grants, patents, and clinical trials, allowing users to explore the interconnectedness of these entities. Once one has signed up for free, one can use the search for free.

The screenshot displays the Dimensions search interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the query "e.g. plastic AND instrument" and a search icon. To the right of the search bar are options for "Save / Export", "Apps", "Support", and a user profile icon labeled "Sayak Bis...".

Below the search bar, there are two main sections: "FILTERS" and "FAVORITES". The "FILTERS" section includes a list of filter categories with expandable arrows: PUBLICATION YEAR, RESEARCHER, RESEARCH CATEGORIES, PUBLICATION TYPE, SOURCE TITLE, JOURNAL LIST, and OPEN ACCESS. Below this list is a "Free Account" section with a "Learn more" button and a footer with "About Dimensions - LinkedIn - X", "Privacy policy - Cookie settings - Legal terms", and "© 2024 Digital Science & Research Solutions, Inc."

The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column shows a list of publication types and their counts: PUBLICATIONS (150,359,853), DATASETS (37,976,085), GRANTS (7,488,812), PATENTS (167,687,132), CLINICAL TRIALS (918,731), POLICY DOCUMENTS (2,482,712), and REPORTS (1,197,278). Below this list, there is a section for "Title, Author(s), Bibliographic reference - About the metrics" with a "Show abstract" checkbox and a "Sort by: Publication date" dropdown. Two sample publication entries are shown, each with a "View PDF", "Add to Library", "Chat with PDF", and "Summarize" button.

The right column is titled "ANALYTICAL VIEWS" and contains a "RESEARCH CATEGORIES" section with a dropdown arrow. Below this is a table of research categories with their respective citation counts:

Research Category	Citation Count
32 Biomedical and Clinical Sciences	33,339,525
40 Engineering	19,664,681
3202 Clinical Sciences	14,277,192
31 Biological Sciences	11,475,786
34 Chemical Sciences	9,510,686

Below the table is an "OVERVIEW" section with a dropdown arrow. It features a line graph showing "Citations" (2.04 B) and "Citations (Mean)" (13.57) from 2015 to 2024. The graph shows a steady increase in citations over the period.

Fig: User interface for searching in Dimensions

1. Search Interface

The user interface of Dimensions is designed to be intuitive and user-friendly, preserving familiar characteristics found in traditional search engines while extending capabilities to explore contextual data. Key features include:

- **Search Bar:** Users can enter keywords, phrases, or specific queries related to their research interests.
- **Faceted Search:** The search results can be refined using various filters, such as publication type, date range, and research field, allowing users to narrow down their results effectively.

2. Publication Index

The core of the Dimensions database is its publication index, which includes a wide range of scholarly outputs, such as:

- Research articles
- Books and book chapters
- Conference proceedings

This index is continuously updated to ensure that users have access to the latest research.

3. Contextual Search Capabilities

Dimensions goes beyond traditional search mechanisms by providing contextual information about research outputs. This includes:

- **Linking Entities:** Each publication can be linked to related entities, such as grants, patents, and clinical trials. For example, a publication may reference a grant that funded the research, or a patent that resulted from the findings.
- **Analytical Views:** Users can access an "Analytical Views" tab that aggregates data related to their search results, providing insights into funding sources, altmetric attention, and collaborations.

4. API and Advanced Search Features

For users requiring more direct access to the data, Dimensions offers an API (Application Programming Interface) that allows for advanced querying. Key features include:

- **Domain-Specific Language (DSL):** The API is designed to be user-friendly, enabling users to query the database without needing to understand its underlying structure. Users can formulate queries based on their intuitive understanding of relationships between different research entities.
- **Example Queries:** Users can perform complex searches, such as finding publications related to specific topics (e.g., "CRISPR") within a defined timeframe and associated with particular institutions.

5. Free and Paid Versions

Dimensions offers both a free version and a subscription-based version (Dimensions Plus). The free version provides access to the publication index and basic search functionalities, while the paid version includes:

- Extended search capabilities across grants, patents, and clinical trials.
- Enhanced analytical tools and metrics for deeper insights into research outputs.

The search mechanisms in Dimensions are designed to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the research landscape. By integrating various types of research outputs and providing contextual information, Dimensions enhances the user experience and supports informed decision-making in research evaluation. The combination of an intuitive interface, advanced search capabilities, and a robust API makes Dimensions a valuable tool for researchers, evaluators, and the academic community at large.

Fig: Dimensions Database (2019) (source: Hook et al., 2018, fig. 2)

Advanced Search

The **advanced search** option in Dimensions allows users to create more complex, keyword-based search queries. This feature is available in Dimensions Analytics and offers several ways to refine searches:

1. **Search in Specific Metadata Fields:** Users can restrict their search to specific metadata fields such as title, acknowledgements, author names, date ranges, or bibliometric indicators.
2. **Search Fields:** To access this feature, click into the search box at the top, then on "Advanced" at the bottom-right. Select a search field from the drop-down menu, enter a value (e.g., date range, keyword, phrase), and click "Add" to include this partial query in the overall search.

- Boolean Queries:** Users can combine queries in multiple fields using Boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT) to create more precise searches.
- Search Indices:** The advanced search allows users to search within specific indices such as "Full Data" or "Title and Abstract," which include various metadata fields.
- Fields and Content Types:** The tutorial lists available fields and content types, with examples for each. Fields include abstract, acknowledgements, Altmetric Attention Score, application number, CPC group, and expiration date.

Exploring The Dimensions Search Language (DSL)

The DSL enables precise and sophisticated queries, making it easier to interact with and analyze the rich dataset provided by Dimensions.

- Basic Query Structure:** It explains the fundamental components of a DSL query, which include a search phrase indicating the scientific records to be searched, and one or more return phrases specifying the contents and structure of the desired results.

The simplest valid DSL query is of the form `search <source>|return <result>`:

```
[3]: %%dsldf
search grants return grants limit 5
```

Returned Grants: 5 (total = 6115921)
Time: 0.73s

```
[3]:
```

	active_year	end_date	funders	funding_org_name	grant_number	id	language	original_title	start_date	start_year	title
0	[2022, 2023, 2024, 2025, 2026, 2027]	2027-12-01	[[acronym: 'ARC', 'city_name': 'Canberra', 'l...	Australian Research Council	FL210100107	grant.9782236	en	Tracking nanoparticles: from cell culture to i...	2022-12-01	2022	Tracking nanoparticles: from cell culture to i...
1	[2022, 2023]	2023-05-31	[[acronym: 'NSF GEO', 'city_name': 'Arlingto...	Directorate for Geosciences	2127438	grant.9752271	en	NNA Planning: Developing community frameworks ...	2022-12-01	2022	NNA Planning: Developing community frameworks ...
2	[2022, 2023, 2024, 2025, 2026, 2027]	2027-11-30	[[acronym: 'ERC', 'city_name': 'Brussels', 'l...	European Research Council	101019146	grant.9708025	en	Seeking Constraints on Open Ocean Biocalifica...	2022-12-01	2022	Seeking Constraints on Open Ocean Biocalifica...
3	[2022, 2023, 2024, 2025, 2026, 2027]	2027-11-30	[[acronym: 'ERC', 'city_name': 'Brussels', 'l...	European Research Council	101003021	grant.9661402	en	New frontiers in advanced glycotherapy for cancer	2022-12-01	2022	New frontiers in advanced glycotherapy for cancer
4	[2022, 2023, 2024, 2025]	2025-10-31	[[acronym: 'NSF MPS', 'city_name': 'Arlingto...	Directorate for Mathematical & Physical Sciences	2105918	grant.9890102	en	RUI: Exciton-Phonon Interactions in Solids bas...	2022-11-15	2022	RUI: Exciton-Phonon Interactions in Solids bas...

- Full-Text Searching:** various aspects of full-text searching, including searching within specific indexes, using search terms, Boolean operators, wildcard searches, and proximity searches.

Full text search works by using search indexes, which can be targeting specific sections of a document e.g. its *abstract*, *authors*, *fulltext* etc...

```
[8]: %%dsldf
search publications
in full_data for "moon landing"
return publications limit 5
```

Returned Publications: 5 (total = 198654)
Time: 1.49s

```
[8]:
```

	authors	id	pages	title	type	volume	year	journalId	journal.title	issue
0	[[affiliations: [[city: 'Noumea', 'city_id...]]	pub.1144582099	106194	Estimating post-release mortality of long-line...	article	249	2022	jour.1032122	Fisheries Research	NaN
1	[[affiliations: [[name: 'ESSEC Business Sc...	pub.1141367962	1-20	Optimization in Multimodal Freight Transportat...	article	299	2022	jour.1027009	European Journal of Operational Research	1
2	[[affiliations: [[city: 'Beijing', 'city_i...	pub.1144677835	197-208	Adaptive control of hypersonic vehicles with u...	article	193	2022	jour.1134138	Acta Astronautica	NaN
3	[[affiliations: [[city: 'Shanghai', 'city_...	pub.1144650554	106956	Constructing Highly Tribopositive Elastic Yarn...	article	94	2022	jour.1051417	Nano Energy	NaN
4	[[affiliations: [[city: 'Chengdu', 'city_i...	pub.1144554233	108783	Nonlinear vibration model and response charact...	article	169	2022	jour.1042338	Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing	NaN

- **Field Searching:** It explains how to search for specific fields within the database, allowing users to target particular data points.

```
[22]: %ds1docs publications
```

```
[22]:
```

	sources	field	type	description	is_filter	is_entity	is_facet
0	publications	abstract	string	The publication abstract.	False	False	False
1	publications	acknowledgements	string	The acknowledgements section text as found in ...	False	False	False
2	publications	altmetric	float	Altmetric Attention Score.	True	False	False
3	publications	altmetric_id	integer	Altmetric Publication ID	True	False	False
4	publications	arxiv_id	string	The publications arXiv identifier (e.g. 'arXiv...	True	False	False
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
62	publications	times_cited	integer	Number of citations (note: does not support em...	True	False	True
63	publications	title	string	Title of a publication.	False	False	False
64	publications	type	string	Publication type (one of: article, chapter, pr...	True	False	True
65	publications	volume	string	Publication volume.	True	False	False
66	publications	year	integer	The year for the version of record of publicat...	True	False	True

67 rows x 7 columns

- **Searching for Researchers:** Methods for finding information about researchers are detailed, enabling users to locate specific researchers and their associated data.

This method expects case insensitive phrases, in format "`< firstname >< lastname >`" or reverse order. Note that strings in double quotes that contain nested quotes must always be escaped by a backslash `\`.

```
[36]: %ds1df search publications in authors for "\"Charles Peirce\"" return publications limit 5
```

Returned Publications: 5 (total = 267)
Time: 0.54s

```
[36]:
```

	authors	id	issue	pages	title	type	volume	year	journal.id	journal.title
0	[[{'affiliations': [], 'corresponding': '...', 'cu...'}]]	pub.1141018395	4	81-91	PAP : prolégomènes à une apologie du pragmatisme	article	N° 163	2021	jour.1142204	Cahiers philosophiques
1	[[{'affiliations': [], 'corresponding': '...', 'cu...'}]]	pub.1140830594	NaN	63-71	COMO TEORIZAR	chapter	NaN	2021	NaN	NaN
2	[[{'affiliations': [], 'corresponding': '...', 'cu...'}]]	pub.1140830593	NaN	55-61	INDUÇÃO ABDUTÓRIA	chapter	NaN	2021	NaN	NaN
3	[[{'affiliations': [], 'corresponding': '...', 'cu...'}]]	pub.1137292963	NaN	256-279	37 Lowell Lecture IV	chapter	NaN	2021	NaN	NaN
4	[[{'affiliations': [], 'corresponding': '...', 'cu...'}]]	pub.1137292823	NaN	437-438	Name Index	chapter	NaN	2021	NaN	NaN

- **Returning Results:** This shows how to structure queries to return desired results, ensuring users can extract the information they need.

```
[45]: %ds1df
search publications
return funders limit 5
return research_orgs limit 5
return year
```

Returned Funders: 5
Returned Research_orgs: 5
Returned Year: 20
Time: 3.56s
[Warning] Dataframe created from first available key, but more than one JSON key found: ['funders', 'research_orgs', 'year']

```
[45]:
```

	acronym	city_name	count	country_name	id	latitude	linkout	longitude	name	types	state_name
0	NSFC	Beijing	2619510	China	grid.419696.5	40.005177	[http://www.nsfc.gov.cn/publish/portal1/]	116.339830	National Natural Science Foundation of China	[Government]	NaN
1	EC	Brussels	893414	Belgium	grid.270680.b	50.851650	[http://ec.europa.eu/index_en.htm]	4.363670	European Commission	[Government]	NaN
2	MOST	Beijing	806641	China	grid.424020.0	39.827835	[http://www.most.gov.cn/eng/]	116.316284	Ministry of Science and Technology of the Peop...	[Government]	NaN
3	JSPS	Tokyo	712701	Japan	grid.54432.34	35.687160	[http://www.jsps.go.jp/]	139.740390	Japan Society for the Promotion of Science	[Nonprofit]	NaN
4	NCI	Bethesda	623054	United States	grid.48336.3a	39.004326	[http://www.cancer.gov/]	-77.101190	National Cancer Institute	[Government]	Maryland

- **Aggregations:** Using DSL to aggregate data for analysis is covered, providing users with tools to summarize and analyze large datasets.

In a `return` phrase requesting one or more `facet` results, aggregation operations to perform during faceting can be specified after the facet name(s) by using the keyword `aggregate` followed by a comma-separated list of one or more `indicator` names corresponding to the `source` being searched.

```
[65]: %%dsidf
search publications
  where year > 2010
return research_orgs
  aggregate rcr_avg, altmetric_median limit 5

Returned Research_orgs: 5
Time: 19.81s
```

	altmetric_median	city_name	count	country_name	id	latitude	linkout	longitude	name	rcr_avg	state_name	types	acronym
0	5.0	Cambridge	270683	United States	grid.38142.3c	42.377052	[http://www.harvard.edu/]	-71.116650	Harvard University	2.493135	Massachusetts	[Education]	NaN
1	4.0	Toronto	177499	Canada	grid.17063.33	43.661667	[http://www.utoronto.ca/]	-79.395000	University of Toronto	2.051205	Ontario	[Education]	NaN
2	2.0	Tokyo	174026	Japan	grid.26999.3d	35.713333	[http://www.u-tokyo.ac.jp/en/]	139.762220	University of Tokyo	1.401742	NaN	[Education]	UT
3	2.0	São Paulo	169020	Brazil	grid.11899.38	-23.563051	[http://www5.usp.br/en/]	-46.730103	University of São Paulo	1.357405	NaN	[Education]	USP
4	2.0	Beijing	159195	China	grid.410726.6	39.909058	[http://www.ucas.ac.cn/]	116.250570	University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	1.678706	NaN	[Education]	UCAS

- **Prerequisites:** It lists prerequisites such as installing the Dimcli library and being familiar with the 'Getting Started' tutorial.

```
[2]: !pip install dimcli --quiet

import dimcli
from dimcli.utils import *
import json
import sys
import pandas as pd
#

print("==\nLogging in..")
# https://digital-science.github.io/dimcli/getting-started.html#authentication
ENDPOINT = "https://app.dimensions.ai"
if 'google.colab' in sys.modules:
    import getpass
    KEY = getpass.getpass(prompt='API Key: ')
    dimcli.login(key=KEY, endpoint=ENDPOINT)
else:
    KEY = ""
    dimcli.login(key=KEY, endpoint=ENDPOINT)
dsl = dimcli.Dsl()

Searching config file credentials for 'https://app.dimensions.ai' endpoint..

==
Logging in..
Dimcli - Dimensions API Client (v0.9.6)
Connected to: <https://app.dimensions.ai/api/dsl> - DSL v2.0
Method: dsl.ini file
```

References

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